

Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling

Results and Summary of the START Delphi Survey Round 2

Authors: Luis Lopes & Emese Karácsonyi (La Palma Research Centre)

Date: 20 June 2024

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12179700>

Website: <https://www.start-heproject.com/>

Disclaimer: START is a Horizon Europe project that is co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Table of Contents

Introduction to the START Delphi Survey	3
Statement 1: Design, development and implementation of thermoelectric devices should focus more on reliability of operation than on performance.....	4
Statement 2: An ultimate goal of thermoelectric devices for mass production shall be the focus on developing a device that fits a large variety of applications in a large temperature range.....	4
Statement 3: If synthetic materials (e.g. synthetic tetrahedrite) show better physical and chemical characteristics than natural materials, then the former should be favoured into thermoelectric devices, independently of other benefits that natural materials might have.....	5
Statement 4: The booming of thermoelectric applications still relies on the breakthrough of high performance materials with affordable costs. With the existing materials and manufacturing methods, new use cases are yet to be explored and might still be in the niche markets.	6
Statement 5: A renaissance of space-related applications might boost the development of thermoelectric energy harvesting technology. But it might not lead directly to large scale implementation in industry, due to the large difference in the working conditions and design principles.	6
Statement 6: A fully-fledged thermoelectric value chain based on tetrahedrites will not be in the market by 2030. However, for long term success, the core stages (e.g. material ZT, functional devices, lower costs, proven operation) of this value chain need to be commercially and feasibility detailed by then.	7
Question 1: What metrics should be used throughout the thermoelectrics value chain as commercial and feasibility indicators?	8
Question 2: What regulatory factors could either facilitate or impede the deployment of thermoelectric technologies?	8
Question 3: In how many year(s)/what timeframe could thermoelectric technologies become commercially competitive with other energy conversion methods?	9
Question 4: Very high ZT values arising from research activities do not help to grow practical thermoelectric applications. Should the community focus on thermoelectric materials with moderate ZT and make commercial and feasibility studies based on their inclusion to speed up commercialization and marketization of thermoelectric generators?	9
Annex – Comments from experts to the statements and questions	11

Introduction to the START Delphi Survey

The START project deployed the Delphi survey as a complementary foresight tool to measure the maturity of the project concept, providing chances for potential improvements that might become necessary along the project evolution, with major focus on the technological, business and economy aspects. The Delphi survey methodology has been designed as a forecasting technique to support technological development and implementation for many technology lines. The main aim is to drive the participants to a consensus on different topics, throughout statements and questions, made in two or more rounds. This technique is anonymous, building on group communication, so that the process is effective in allowing a group of individuals, as a whole, to deal with a complex problem or question (Linstone and Turoff, 2002). In a Delphi process, experts (the participants) are asked to consider and classify a number of questions or statements.

The Delphi process is different from other types of surveys and questionnaires. First, a list of relevant interested experts is pre-compiled. Second, there is a possibility for experts to comment and explain their opinion on any of the statements. Third, answers are analysed, statistics built and shared with the experts for further comments, resulting in new rounds of questions. Finally, the objective of a Delphi is to reach a consensus within the expert pool.

The START Delphi Survey was built in two rounds between the months of October 2023 and April 2024, with round 1 running between October and November 2023 and round 2 between March and April 2024. It was used as a way to engage with experts and collect their views and opinions in areas of interest to START and that are relevant for the project development both during and after the funding period. The survey ultimately addressed the current and future states of the thermoelectric field and the future of START, as a new technology line based on tetrahedrite thermoelectric modules and systems, entwined with topics such as sustainability, energy generation and economics.

This document presents the Delphi Survey Round 2 statements and questions, and the opinions and views of experts.

Statement 1: Design, development and implementation of thermoelectric devices should focus more on reliability of operation than on performance.

Summary: Experts tend more to disagree than agree with the statement, in the basis that both reliability and performance should be considered of equal importance in the development and implementation processes of TE devices and technology, and should, therefore, see improvements at the same time. However, it is also mentioned that the importance of reliability and performance in thermoelectric devices varies based on end-user needs, so there are cases where reliability does take precedence over performance and efficiency, and while the latter are not TE’s biggest selling points, there still needs to be criteria for performance. The example of waste heat conversion is cited, where reliability of operation is more important than performance. However, in scenarios with high heat costs, performance could be prioritized.

Ultimately, it is mostly agreed that a balance between reliability and performance is desired for a successful design and implementation of TE devices in its applications.

Statement 2: An ultimate goal of thermoelectric devices for mass production shall be the focus on developing a device that fits a large variety of applications in a large temperature range.

Summary: A divisive statement that depicts the divergence of opinions about the development of devices that can be used across different temperature ranges. Arguments in favor of such an approach mention

the current situation with the use of bismuth telluride (BiTe, one of the most common materials in TE devices, toxic and expensive), that it will be helpful to enhance the market demand and, consequently, the mass production of tetrahedrite-based TE and that waste heat is very variable and a transversal device could be implemented in several applications. On the other hand, arguments against an approach to develop one device that fits all temperature ranges mention that it would be better and more realistic to have different devices targeting difference applications, that most of the applications suit in a short temperature range, and that developing a broad range of devices, each fit for a certain range of temperatures, and all devices together covering a broad range of temperatures would be a better approach.

Statement 3: If synthetic materials (e.g. synthetic tetrahedrite) show better physical and chemical characteristics than natural materials, then the former should be favoured into thermoelectric devices, independently of other benefits that natural materials might have.

Summary: Opinions on the preference of synthetic materials over natural ones are scattered. While some experts offer arguments in favour, others offer arguments against this view. The first group states reasons including that performance and reliability are key and not the source of the material used, and that TE devices should always use the better cost-effective material to save cost on the system aspects, independently on the source of material. Naturally occurring minerals are characterised by a wide variety of chemical compositions and thus low repeatability of thermoelectric parameters. The cost of homogenising the physico-chemical parameters of natural minerals to make them suitable for production can be very high, even higher than the cost of synthetic materials.

These points are counterbalanced with the idea that if the difference is not that significant (and the performance of natural materials is within the expected range), nowadays other benefits as circular economy and sustainability are very critical in product development and quality/environmental certification, for example, that complex trade-off between costs, legislation and sustainability aspects and their respective weighting, that the scale of performance will dictate the winner. The benefits of using natural materials (e.g. lower environmental costs of manufacturing) may outweigh the gains of using synthetic materials.

Ultimately, it is mostly agreed that the selection of one over the other is a component of many factors (geological, environmental, material, application, etc.).

Statement 4: The booming of thermoelectric applications still relies on the breakthrough of high performance materials with affordable costs. With the existing materials and manufacturing methods, new use cases are yet to be explored and might still be in the niche markets.

Summary: Participants mostly agree that TE is still scarcely applied and that there are opportunities still to uncover in many fields. A widespread use of TE seems to be hindered by the current material choices for TE devices, since they are not robust or efficient enough (e.g., contacts are too fragile and prone to thermal degradation, obliging the designers to work with bypass valves and other complicated system issues). Disagreement comments state that the performance of known materials is already quite sufficient for mass production of devices and for wider implementation in end-user applications.

Statement 5: A renaissance of space-related applications might boost the development of thermoelectric energy harvesting technology. But it might not lead directly to large scale implementation in industry, due to the large difference in the working conditions and design principles.

Summary: Experts tend to believe that space applications of TE devices can be a flagship for the widespread use of the technology in other applications. Despite this positive outcome, it is important to

note that working conditions and requirements between space and terrestrial applications are quite different. Disagreement comments state that both space and terrestrial applications require high efficiency (high-zT) materials. Space applications can support non-recurrent engineering costs that terrestrial applications can benefit from, and call for a universal technical solution that can be used in any field.

Statement 6: A fully-fledged thermoelectric value chain based on tetrahedrites will not be in the market by 2030. However, for long term success, the core stages (e.g. material ZT, functional devices, lower costs, proven operation) of this value chain need to be commercially and feasibility detailed by then.

Summary: Experts mostly agree that the journey from material development to practical applications in thermoelectric technology is a lengthy and ongoing process. While they also consider tetrahedrite as a source material as a potential option for large-scale applications, they're not the only material and still need to prove their positive performance in devices and applications. Since tetrahedrite based TE devices and systems haven't been commercially shown at large, focus should be on the development of proven materials instead before 2030.

Question 1: What metrics should be used throughout the thermoelectrics value chain as commercial and feasibility indicators?

Summary: The considerations for evaluating thermoelectric devices and systems encompass various factors as suggested by experts:

Commercial & Economic indicators:

- Return on Investment, Number of Years to achieve Return on Investment
- Levelized Cost of Energy
- Energy payback time
- Produced kWh/cost of TE production
- Cost, Cost-benefit-ratio of the overall device, Power-cost ratio
- €/W as CAPEX for TEGs
- Total cost of ownership including upstream and downstream technologies (heat exchangers, connectors, power electronics, power storage, etc.)
- Nominal power per costs of production (W/€ for end-users)
- Device lifetime/price
- Thermo-emf
- Base/Raw Materials quantities available for TE applications
- CO2 savings
- LCA indicators such as initial CO2 emissions per W, reliability on critical or nonrenewable raw materials

Feasibility and Performance indicators:

- Useful lifetime, Service life in working hours
- Performance, Efficiency in energy conversion
- Toxicity
- zT for materials
- Power factor (or output), Power generation of the TEG
- Maximum temperature for thermal stability
- W/K for devices
- Stability and reliability factors
- Power/heat density
- Working temperature
- Thermal efficiency

Question 2: What regulatory factors could either facilitate or impede the deployment of thermoelectric technologies?

Summary: The following regulatory factors were mentioned by experts as those of having the possibility to impact the deployment of thermoelectric technologies:

- Thermoelectric energy systems and production should be clearly defined as green energy.

- Political factors such as more restrictive regulations or bans on the import of raw materials (like Bi, Te, Ge (as a recent case from China)), Legislation regarding tailings recovery/reprocessing of raw materials, Regulations on elimination of hazardous materials such as Pb, the allowed use of insoluble lead compounds, like PbTe and PbS (these are not absorbed and have low toxicity), in TE devices, Seeing similar support as photovoltaic energy (e.g. subsidies or fiscal advantages for producers as well as final consumers, increased funding for research).
- Economic factors such as energy prices (high energy prices favour TE application), Reduced prices or bigger discounts to acquire TE devices, Carbon taxes, Taxes on waste heat (which now is free), Low efficiency of TE devices (due to a lack of concept regarding their structure).
- Societal factors such as a Common desire for the renewable and green energy products and, Public support to communication towards adopters.

Question 3: In how many year(s)/what timeframe could thermoelectric technologies become commercially competitive with other energy conversion methods?

Summary: Most experts believe that TE devices, systems and technologies, relying or not on tetrahedrite, could become commercially competitive with other energy conversion methods in between a 5- and 15-years' timeframe. Their reasoning for this includes the decision on which energy conversion methods/technologies to be used (making it so that it should take at least 10 years to surpass photovoltaics), that it also depends on the application (with some applications being earlier or later competitive), but that TE technologies should focus on niche applications where other competitors cannot become competitive in 10 years (competition with thermodynamic cycles will remain very challenging in the next years). Finally, experts state that for most TEGs the current TRL is 5-6, meaning that they still need 5 more years of R+D+I to reach TRL 7-8 and then 5 more years to reach TRL 9 (fully commercial).

Yet, some experts state that this timeframe could be reduced to 2 years (e.g., the START case, if a device is developed in 2024, then it could be implemented in 2-3 years) or could be as much as 50 years (this being due the lacking or low level of financial support for the development of thermoelectric technology, at current levels of economic investment and political framework. The discovery of novel TE materials or the discovery of a widely usable application can greatly change the latter timeframe to a more reduced one of around 10 or less years.

One last comment of relevance is that TE technology can only be competitive with other energy methods if it focuses on waste heat recovery.

Question 4: Very high ZT values arising from research activities do not help to grow practical thermoelectric applications. Should the community focus on thermoelectric materials with moderate ZT and make commercial and feasibility studies based on their inclusion to speed up commercialization and marketization of thermoelectric generators?

Generally, experts agree that the thermoelectric community and TE value chains should focus more on materials with moderate zT and develop commercial and feasibility studies for these, instead of hoping for the "golden goose" of TE materials and/or application. They see that this is the best way forward since it can give a maximum of applications for the general society, since device design and sustainable

manufacturing are as important as the zT, incentivizing more efforts to be made in the near future towards these aspects. Experts also believe that commercial and feasibility studies should be developed as early as possible for materials and, that the engineering of a complete TEG, with less focus on TE materials, could help speeding up the realization of reliable harvesters. Focus on reproducibility, engineering and material issues (e.g., contacts, T-gradient stability), as well as the belief that cheap materials should be the focus as research, are also highlighted. that zT is important but reliable integration in functioning systems is indispensable. An interesting comment states that systems developed with lower zT materials will afterwards be easy to upgrade with higher zT materials, if (when)ever they become available, supporting another comment that zT is important but reliable integration in functioning systems is indispensable.

On the other hand, experts against the value of this statement say that high zT material values are essential in research and for practical applications, that there still needs to be a continuous focus on improving efficiency (since low performance will be unacceptable in some applications), that a full bandwidth of research is required (i.e., people for the visions and the high zT, people for technological feasibility and people for device integration), that commercialization can be very challenging with poor power performance, that together high zT, contact resistance and stability are also needed. In their view, high zT and commercialization should be sought together.

Annex – Comments from experts to the statements and questions

Statement 1: Design, development and implementation of thermoelectric devices should focus more on reliability of operation than on performance.

Agreement comments:

- This is actually dependent the purpose of end-users, at some cases, the reliability and performance will be both important.
- Efficiency is not the core selling point of TE anyway.
- Agree but there must still be a criteria for the performance.
- Both factors are very important. The decision on which is more important depends on the particular application of the device. In the case of a device for the conversion of free waste heat, performance and efficiency appear to be less important in relation to reliability. However, in situations where the cost of heat is high, performance may take priority over reliability.
- Performance is important but comes second. Top level ZT for instance is of no use if devices breakdown at the first occasion.

Neutral comments:

- Both, reliability of operation and performance are equally important.
- These two criteria (reliability and performance) are important and necessary (not one more than the other one).

Disagreement comments:

- The focus should be on both.
- It should focus on both.
- Both are important to consider in the design, development and implementation of TE devices.
- Performance is also key.
- Still performance needs to improve in order to make it competitive.
- A device with low efficiency may be reliable, but will not be used because the low output will make its application impractical.
- The most important criterion is the thermal efficiency. If this is low, you will never recover the energy that goes into fabricating the recovery system itself.
- The weak point of thermoelectric devices is low performance, which hinders their mass application.

Statement 2: An ultimate goal of thermoelectric devices for mass production shall be the focus on developing a device that fits a large variety of applications in a large temperature range.

Agreement comments:

- With BiTe it is already the case, but in the RT range.
- I agree that it will be helpful to enhance the market demand and, consequently, the mass production of TE. But if the device could have a good performance even in a more specific temperature range, that will be important for the mass production as well (furthermore, within a more limited temperature range, can exist several applications to use the TE device).
- This should be important because waste heat is very variable.

Neutral comments:

- Thermoelectric is a very flexible technology due to its very high power efficiency. It is easy to adjust its design to various applications.
- It can be a small number of smaller T-ranges.

Disagreement comments:

- It is not possible to develop one device that fits all temperature ranges.
- TE devices will dedicated to specific temperatures range applications and cannot be optimized for a large temperature range. It has not to be the ultimate goal of TE devices.
- No necessarily one device for everything. It would be much better and also realistic to have different devices targeting difference applications.
- Most of the applications suit in a not very large range, close to ambient temperatures.
- I believe that there is a huge demand for low-temperature thermoelectric heat converters, which economically justifies the mass production of such devices.
- The focus should not be to develop "a" (= one) device for a broad range of temperatures, but to develop a broad range of devices, each fit for a certain range of temperatures, and all devices together covering a broad range of temperatures. In other words, a "one size fits all" TE device will never be.

Statement 3: If synthetic materials (e.g. synthetic tetrahedrite) show better physical and chemical characteristics than natural materials, then the former should be favoured into thermoelectric devices, independently of other benefits that natural materials might have.

Agreement comments:

- Performance and repeatability are key.
- If the cost of the material is a substantial part of the cost of the system, the design is wrong. Always pick the better material, and save cost on the system aspects.

Neutral comments:

- It is necessary to have knowledge of the % of difference in the characteristics between synthetic and natural materials. Because if the difference is not that significant (and the performance of natural materials is within the expected range), nowadays other benefits such as circular economy and sustainability are very critical in product development and quality/environmental certification, for example.
- Complex trade-off between costs, legislation and sustainability aspects and their respective weighting.
- Depends on the scale of performance improvement.
- On the one hand, naturally occurring minerals are characterised by a wide variety of chemical compositions and thus low repeatability of thermoelectric parameters. The cost of homogenising the physico-chemical parameters of natural minerals to make them suitable for production can be very high, even higher than the cost of synthetic materials. On the other hand, the benefits of using natural materials (e.g. lower environmental costs of manufacturing) may outweigh the gains of using synthetic materials. The outcome is a component of many factors (geological, environmental, material, application, etc.).
- The question is not quantified. it must be balanced.
- An invention has been proposed that does not require expensive materials to increase ZT.

Disagreement comments:

- The aim of START project is supply natural thetraedrite obtained from mining wates in orther to reduce them.

Statement 4: The booming of thermoelectric applications still relies on the breakthrough of high performance materials with affordable costs. With the existing materials and manufacturing methods, new use cases are yet to be explored and might still be in the niche markets.

Agreement comments:

- There's still room for new applications.
- The current materials clearly have not led to a boom in applications.
- Current materials are not robust or efficient enough: contacts are too fragile and prone to thermal degradation, obliging the designers to work with bypass vales and other complicated system issues. Unless very robust thermoelectric metals can be developed with moderate ZT (say 0.7), only very efficient (high ZT, say 2 or more) semiconductors give enough power output to justify the system complexity.

Disagreement comments:

- In my opinion, the performance of known materials is already quite sufficient for mass production of devices.

- An invention has been proposed that does not require expensive materials to increase ZT.

Statement 5: A renaissance of space-related applications might boost the development of thermoelectric energy harvesting technology. But it might not lead directly to large scale implementation in industry, due to the large difference in the working conditions and design principles.

Agreement comments:

- TEGs in space are coupled with fissile material, like plutonium-238, and this is not directly linked to the renaissance of space industry.
- different requirements for space and non-space applications.
- I believe there's much to do with not that high temperatures. Close to "ambient" till 250°C.
- Conditions in space are radically different from those encountered on Earth.

Neutral comments:

- It depends on the materials that are found. Very high cost materials optimized for high temperatures may not lead to energy harvesting applications.

Disagreement comments:

- Both space and terrestrial applications require high efficiency (high-ZT) materials. Space applications can support non-recurrent engineering costs that terrestrial applications can benefit from.
- Develop a universal technical solution that can be used in any field.

Statement 6: A fully-fledged thermoelectric value chain based on tetrahedrites will not be in the market by 2030. However, for long term success, the core stages (e.g. material ZT, functional devices, lower costs, proven operation) of this value chain need to be commercially and feasibility detailed by then.

Agreement comments:

- It is a long road from materials development, still not complete to applications.

Neutral comments:

- It is important to push the commercially and feasibility of the core stages of TE value chains, but I do not know if, by now, it is possible to predict when TE based on tetrahedrite will be on the market.
- Tetrahedrites are one option for large scale applications, but not the only one.

Disagreement comments:

- The current focus should be on the development of proven materials.
- There is a development that does not require expensive materials.

Question 1: What metrics should be used throughout the thermoelectrics value chain as commercial and feasibility indicators?

- Return of investment.
- Power-cost ratio.
- LCOE.
- Cost-benefit-ratio of the overall device.
- Years, considering ROI.
- Efficiency in energy conversion, useful lifetime, EPT (energy payback time), produced kWh/cost of TE production.
- Cost, performance, toxicity.
- ZT, power factor, maximum temperature for thermal stability.
- ZT for materials; W/K for devices; W/€ for end-users.
- Conversion efficiency and long term stability.
- Power generation of the TEG.
- ZT, power factor, reliability factor, power/heat density.
- ZT, cost, stability, working temperature.
- Thermal efficiency and power output.
- Nominal power per costs of production (ie Watt/EUR).
- Power/price; device life-time/price.
- Thermo-emf, output parameters of the device.
- €/W for a given temperature difference, CO₂ savings, Base/Raw Materials quantities available for TE applications.
- €/W as CAPEX for TEGs ; service life in working hours ; total cost of ownership including upstream and downstream technologies (heat exchangers, connectors, power electronics, power storage... ; return on investment ; LCA indicators such as initial CO₂ emissions per W, reliability on critical or non renewable raw materials.
- ZT.

Question 2: What regulatory factors could either facilitate or impede the deployment of thermoelectric technologies?

- It is essential that thermoelectric technologies are well known and they should be considered as green energy.
- Political, economic.
- Cost.
- E.g. energy price.
- "More restrictive regulations on the import of elements (like Bi, Te) favours tetrahedrites
- Higher energy costs also favours tetrahedrites".
- legislation regarding tailings recovery/reprocessing, preference by renewable and green energy technologies.
- Limitation of raw materials.
- Carbon taxes, tax on waste heat.
- Increasing electricity prices would favor TE waste heat recovery.
- Availability and sustainability.
- It depends on the application and the material.
- Regulations on elimination of hazardous materials such as Pb.

- Facilitate: allow the use of UNSOLUBLE led compounds, like PbTe and PbS. They are not absorbed and have low toxicity. If PbS were poisonous, there would be no life on earth since it is abundant in the ground.
- The development of thermoelectric technology should be similarly supported as photovoltaic technology (subsidies for producers as well as final consumers, increased funding for research).
- Low efficiency of thermoelectric devices: The low efficiency of thermoelectric devices is due to a lack of concept regarding their structure.
- Carbon and Energy prices.
- Facilitate: public subsidies or fiscal advantages; public support to communication towards adopters - Impede: restriction of use of certain critical raw materials; export bans from sourcing countries, e.g. recent Chinese ban on Germanium.

Question 3: In how many year(s)/what timeframe could thermoelectric technologies become commercially competitive with other energy conversion methods?

- 10.
- 10: depends on which energy conversion methods/technologies, should be more than 10 yrs versus photovoltaics.
- 2.
- It is not competitive, it is the alternative when the other conversion methods are not applicable
- I do not have knowledge to answer this question.
- 10.
- 10.
- 2 to 10, depending on the application.
- It has to be compared to other conversion methods: inputs and environments conditions are different. TE technology has to be competitive with its own criteria and performances.
- After five years.
- Hard to predict - it requires the discovery of novel TE materials and/or direct application.
- It depends on the application. I expect it to be 2 - 5 years.
- This is unknown. It depends on the development of better materials.
- 5 years.
- Depends on the level of financial support for the development of thermoelectric technology. At current levels of investment, it could be 50-100 years. At support levels like for photovoltaics - even less than 10 years.
- it can be competitive providing it uses waste heat.
- When we implement the proposed thermoelectric device, this will happen in 2-3 years, and maybe earlier. In case of carrying out the development of the device this year.
- 10: Competition with thermodynamic cycles will remain very challenging. TE technologies should focus on niche applications where other competitors cannot compete.
- 10-15: For most TEGs, current TRL is 5-6, 5 years R+D+I to reach 7-8 and 10 to reach 9.
- Within 10 years.

Question 4: Very high ZT values arising from research activities do not help to grow practical thermoelectric applications. Should the community focus on thermoelectric materials with moderate ZT and make commercial and feasibility studies based on their inclusion to speed up commercialization and marketization of thermoelectric generators?

- Yes: We understand that the aim of the development of this technology is to have a maximum of applications for the general society.
- Of course: device design and sustainable manufacturing are as important as the ZT, which need more efforts to be made in the near future.
- High zT values are fundamental.
- yes, especially half-heusler and skutterudite materials.
- The engineering of complete TEG, with less focus on TE materials, could help speeding up the realisation of reliable harvesters.
- It could be a good strategy, but without losing focus on trying to improve TE performance.
- Not completely, low performance is not acceptable for many applications.
- Yes.
- I reckon the full bandwidth of research is required: people for the visions and the high zTs, people for technological feasibility and people for device integration.
- High ZT values measured in R&D laboratory and presented in scientific paper have to be treated cautiously. If measurements have been validated (performed several times, and validated by other laboratory), they have also to be kept for long time. And it is clearly not the case currently for all high ZT presented in literature. That is the reason why commercial and feasibility studies are not conclusive.
- I think it is still essential to explore high ZT materials. Commercialization can be very challenging with poor power performance.
- And not only focus on high temperature.
- It is important to focus on reproducibility which is lacking for some reported very high ZT materials.
- No: The high ZT give high power and this is seminal. Contact resistance and stability are the second necessary condition for success.
- Yes, I believe that commercial and feasibility studies can bring the commercialisation of thermoelectric devices significantly closer even with the current ZT.
- Yes, there are a number of engineering and material issues that need to be resolved, contacts, T-gradient stability.
- Use the cheapest materials.: Research and search for new expensive materials with high ZT are leading away from the solution of efficient thermoelectric devices.
- No. Both ways (high ZT and commercialisable devices) should be investigated in parallel.
- Yes, ZT is important but reliable integration in functioning systems is indispensable. This must be developed without waiting for the miracle material with high ZT. Systems developed will afterwards be easy to upgrade with higher ZT materials, if ever they one day become available.